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Photonic and quantum thermometry using active resonator compound semiconductor photonic integrated circuits

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Semiconductors are extremely useful for temperature sensing owing to the strong temperature dependence of their optical and electronic properties. Silicon, the most widely used semiconductor, underpins modern electronics and is increasingly important in integrated photonics, offering a cost-effective platform for optical sensors. Silicon-based ring resonator (RR) temperature sensors operate via the temperature-dependent change in silicon's refractive index (dn/dT), which affects the optical modes in the ring. However, silicon has two main limitations: its indirect band gap makes it a poor light emitter, necessitating external light sources, and its thermal properties are fixed. In contrast, compound semiconductors, such as indium phosphide (InP), gallium arsenide (GaAs), gallium nitride (GaN) and indium arsenide (InAs), have direct band gaps, making them efficient light emitters as commonly used in light-emitting diodes and lasers. Their thermal properties can also be tailored through alloying. These features make them ideal for ‘active resonator’ temperature sensors with integrated light sources, allowing customization for various temperature ranges. This paper focuses on InP-based alloys, highlighting their fundamental properties and potential for integration into active

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quantum well-based heterostructures. These can be fabricated into micro-ring and other resonator designs. Integrating light sources within the sensor enhances both simplicity and functionality, paving the way for versatile temperature sensors suited to a wide range of applications.

This article is part of the Theo Murphy meeting issue ‘The redefined kelvin: progress and prospects’.

1. Fundamentals

Photonic thermometry is an emerging branch of thermometry that exploits the properties of photons and their various interactions with matter to undertake temperature sensing [1]. In this paper, we specifically focus on the known variation of the refractive index of a semiconductor, which can be measured through the use of resonant optical cavities [2]. The underlying principle relies upon the crystalline nature of semiconductors and the fact that the periodic arrangement of atoms in the crystal lattice is perturbed by changes in the lattice temperature. This leads to a corresponding change in many of the fundamental properties of the crystal. Of particular importance to the photonic thermometry¹ under consideration here is the dielectric constant of a crystal that describes how effectively the material can reduce the strength of an electric field within it by becoming polarized. In semiconductor materials, this property plays a crucial role in determining how light propagates through the crystal. Since light is an electromagnetic wave, as it travels through a semiconductor, its oscillating electric field interacts with the electrons bound within the periodic crystal potential. This interaction reduces the phase velocity of the light, which manifests as an increase in the dielectric constant and hence refractive index. The dielectric response and refractive index are influenced by the electronic band structure of the crystal, particularly the band gap. Semiconductors with smaller band gaps (e.g. indium arsenide (InAs)) allow for stronger electronic polarization at lower photon energies, which increases the dielectric constant and refractive index in the transparency region. Conversely, wide band gap materials (e.g. gallium nitride (GaN)) tend to have lower dielectric constants and refractive indices. Thus, the dielectric constant connects the microscopic interaction of light with the electronic environment of the crystal to macroscopic optical properties, making it fundamental in designing and understanding photonic devices.

Temperature has an important effect on the dielectric properties of semiconductors. The refractive index of a semiconductor changes with temperature primarily owing to two effects: thermal expansion of the lattice and the temperature dependence of the electronic band structure. As temperature increases, the crystal lattice expands, reducing the density of atoms and altering the dielectric response. However, more significantly, the band gap of the semiconductor typically decreases with increasing temperature owing to both lattice expansion and increased electron–phonon interactions. As the temperature increases, the atoms in the crystal vibrate more strongly and the lattice expands. This increased inter-atomic spacing weakens the periodic crystal potential that electrons experience, leading to a reduction in the band gap. In addition, electron–phonon interactions become more significant at higher temperatures, further narrowing the band gap. The reduction in the band gap allows a greater electronic polarization in response to an optical field. This enhanced polarization increases the material’s dielectric constant, which in turn raises the refractive index. Together, these effects cause the refractive index to vary with temperature, a property that is key to photonic thermometry.

In general, semiconductors can have either *direct* or *indirect* band gaps, and their simplified light–matter interaction diagram, as shown in figure 1, consists of the conduction band (CB), which is defined as the lowest unoccupied band, and the valence band (VB), which is the

¹We hereafter use the phrase ‘photonic thermometry’ to mean ‘semiconductor-based photonic thermometry’.

highest occupied energy band. At 0 K, the electrons fully occupy the VB, while there are no electrons in the CB. As the temperature increases from 0 K, the electrons in the VB are thermally excited by the thermal energy $k_B T$ (where k_B is the Boltzmann constant²), gaining energy in the CB while leaving a positively charged quasi-particle, a hole in the VB. These electrons and holes are known as charge carriers, carrying a net energy via their respective allowed energy bands in the semiconductors. For a *direct* band gap semiconductor such as indium phosphide (InP), gallium arsenide (GaAs) or InAs, from the group family of III–V materials, electrons and holes can interact strongly with photons as their transitions of photon energy ($h\nu$) between the CB and VBs occur at the same value of the crystal momentum, \mathbf{k} , as shown in [figure 1a](#). In contrast, for the elemental semiconductor silicon (Si), the minimum state of the CB and VB maximum occurs at different values of \mathbf{k} . Silicon is therefore known as an indirect band gap semiconductor, in which carriers can only weakly interact with photons (light), requiring an additional particle known as phonon (energy, $\hbar\omega$) for conservation of momentum and energy, as illustrated in [figure 1b](#). This makes it an unsuitable semiconductor for light emission.

Silicon is the most widely used semiconductor and is essential to electronic devices and passive integrated photonics owing to a combination of its cost-effective and mature processing platform that enables high-density integration over large-scale wafers. Excellent progress has been made in using silicon to develop waveguide systems and wafer-based components such as Bragg gratings, ring resonators (RRs) and photonic crystal cavities for passive photonic thermometers [1]. However, all-silicon-based devices are intrinsically *passive* and require an external light source to enable their operation owing to their indirect band gap. Furthermore, as an elemental semiconductor, silicon has largely fixed optical and thermal properties, hence limiting the range of its applications in temperature sensing. Therefore, this work explores the use of the alternative material system of III–V compound semiconductors (and their alloys) for developing *active* photonic thermometry to overcome the fundamental drawbacks of silicon's indirect band gap, that is, its limited ability to provide an efficient light emitter on chip. The III–V semiconductor family also offers a broad spectral range of operation with extended optical and thermal properties, as shown in [figure 2](#), in which many of the III–V compounds have a direct band gap (closed circles) and therefore are commonly used for light-emitting diodes (LEDs), optical amplifiers, photodetectors and lasers. Such materials have the potential to overcome the intrinsic limitations of silicon and mitigate the need for an additional external light source for use in photonic integrated circuit (PIC) applications such as photonic thermometry. This would reduce the overall size of the device and remove the cumbersome optomechanics required for waveguide coupling between the light source, optical fibre and the chip-scale device, while maximizing the opportunities afforded by fully planar and scalable PICs. Furthermore, it also provides the possibility of combining various material combinations within the group III–V semiconductor alloys, expanding the choice of materials from binary systems towards ternary and quaternary alloys, such as indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) and indium gallium arsenide phosphide (InGaAsP), offering increased flexibility to engineer the optical characteristics of semiconductors for active photonic thermometry. Examples of using alloying to tune the operating wavelength of a semiconductor device are shown by the connecting lines in [figure 2](#) for a variety of alloys. Note that the solid lines correspond to direct band gap alloys, while dashed lines indicate when the alloy has an indirect band gap. This is an important factor to be taken into account when designing an alloy for applications at particular wavelengths.

²Note that in this paper we denote the Boltzmann constant using k_B to differentiate it from other quantities in the paper denoted by k .

Figure 1. Simplified light–matter interaction in semiconductors diagram for (a) direct and (b) indirect band gap, showing the CB and VB energy versus lattice wavevector k relationship (dispersion).

Figure 2. Comparison between silicon and a broad range of group III–V semiconductors at 300 K. (a) Band gap energy, E_g as a function of lattice constant a_0 , where the markers correspond to binary semiconductor materials while the connecting curves indicate the variation with ternary alloy composition. (b) Infrared refractive index as a function of band gap energy (equivalent wavelengths shown above).

2. Temperature dependence of the refractive index

The refractive index of a given semiconductor depends on both the measurement wavelength and temperature. The variation of refractive index with temperature is related to the change in the critical points of the band structure, for example, the band gap. The temperature dependence of the band gap can be modelled using the empirical Varshni equation [3,4], which accounts for the change in inter-atomic spacing of the crystal lattice owing to thermal expansion and the thermal variation of electronic polarizability from electron and lattice interactions:

$$E_g(T) = E_g(T = 0) - \frac{\alpha T^2}{T + \beta}, \quad (2.1)$$

where α and β are adjustable Varshni coefficients, E_g is the energy band gap (which can be used for either direct or indirect semiconductor materials) and T is thermodynamic temperature. For photon energies sufficiently far below the band gap (into transparency), the refractive index tends towards a constant value approximating the square root of the optical dielectric constant ($n \approx \sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{opt}}}$), referred to here as the infrared model [5].

As the band gap changes with temperature (dE_g/dT), the corresponding change in refractive index with temperature dn/dT for a given semiconductor is known as its thermo-optic coefficient and is usually observed to be on the order of 10^{-3} to 10^{-6} per $^\circ\text{C}$ [4]. These thermo-optic coefficients represent an essential optical property in the design and characterization of

photonic devices, and so significant effort has historically been made to both measure and theoretically calculate their values for a range of technologically important materials [6–11].

One such empirical relation, proposed by Ravindra *et al.* [12], expresses the general inverse relationship observed between dn/dT and dE_g/dT :

$$\frac{dn}{dT}(T) = -0.62 \frac{dE_g}{dT}(T). \quad (2.2)$$

This provides a convenient method of estimating the nonlinear effect of the thermal redshift in the band gap from equation (2.1) on the refractive index. Figure 3a shows the temperature dependence of the band gap, calculated using equation (2.1) with typical parameters for GaAs, InP, Si and InAs [4], alongside the corresponding refractive index calculated using equation (2.2). For each semiconductor, increasing temperature increases lattice vibrations and hence causes the band gap to reduce (figure 3a), while the infrared refractive index (figure 3b) exhibits an inverse relationship with the band gap, increasing as the temperature increases. Figure 3c shows the temperature dependence of the thermo-optic coefficients in each semiconductor, extracted from the derivative of $n(T)$ in figure 3b.

From figure 3, it is clear that $n(T)$ and dn/dT are both temperature dependent, whereby the temperature sensitivity decreases at low temperature. As the temperature decreases and goes below the Debye temperature, the phonon mode density decreases, leading to a smaller change in band gap and hence refractive index with temperature. It is also clear that the temperature sensitivity is semiconductor dependent. This suggests that the choice of semiconductor is important in a photonic thermometry application, both in terms of sensitivity and operating temperature range.

There are multiple methods used to measure the refractive index dispersion of semiconductor materials, of which ellipsometry is the most useful [9–11,13–15]. However, there are relatively few reports on the temperature dependence of the refractive index and rarely as a function of wavelength and/or composition. Below the material band gap, the refractive index dispersion is often interpolated using the Sellmeier model [16–19] of the form

$$n^2(\lambda, T) - 1 = \sum_i \frac{B_i(T) \lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - C_i(T)}, \quad (2.3)$$

where λ is the wavelength in vacuum and B_i and C_i are the Sellmeier coefficients [19], which are used to generate a fit to the experimental data [16–18,20] and hence to develop a model of $n(\lambda, T)$. For the III–V semiconductors of interest to this study on photonic thermometry, there is relatively little relevant data. Hence, a comprehensive analysis of the InP, GaAs, gallium phosphide (GaP) and InAs binary semiconductor refractive index temperature-dependent dispersion is discussed here.

3. Temperature-dependent refractive index measurements using spectroscopic ellipsometry

As discussed above, we specifically focus on developing an active photonic thermometry approach by exploiting compound group III–V semiconductor materials. We focus here on InP-based semiconductors as both active light emitters and passive waveguiding components for temperature sensing. This material system is compatible with the standard wavelength of 1550 nm conventionally used in optical fibre telecommunications and is additionally suitable for heterogeneous integration with silicon devices [1]. Since InP is a mature active semiconductor, it has been extensively used in infrared devices such as telecommunications lasers, in which the quaternary InGaAsP alloys can be grown with a choice of suitable compositions and refractive indices on InP for near-infrared active devices [4,21–23]. Prior to any optical

Figure 3. Thermal properties of GaAs, InP, Si and InAs, showing the temperature dependence of (a) band gap, (b) long-wavelength (infrared) refractive index, (c) thermo-optic coefficient.

and photonic design, it is essential to establish refractive index data from accurate measurements of the semiconductor materials system used in designing the waveguides, resonators and lasers. Theoretical and experimental studies on the refractive indices of III–V semiconductors have historically been made to propose models to express their refractive index dispersions at various compositions, band gaps and temperatures [23–27]. However, most experimental studies of the refractive indices of III–V semiconductors have been limited to room temperature or a narrow selection of temperatures. Therefore, spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE) measurements were used [11] to derive the temperature-dependent refractive indices of III–V materials such as InP, InAs, GaP and GaAs over a wavelength range from 800 to 1800 nm at temperatures ranging from 298.15 to 473.15 K (25–200°C). SE [28–30] is highly sensitive to even very thin (less than 50 nm) surface films [30] owing to its measurement of the change of polarization, determining the relative phase change of either reflected or transmitted polarized light. A known polarization of light is reflected or transmitted from the sample, and the change in polarization is measured by two ellipsometry parameters Ψ and Δ , which are described in terms of the ratio of complex Fresnel coefficients, R_p/R_s in reflection or T_p/T_s in transmission, for the parallel (p- in plane of incidence) and perpendicular (s- perpendicular plane of incidence) polarized light [28–30] as

$$\rho = \frac{R_p}{R_s} = \tan(\Psi) \cdot e^{i\Delta}. \quad (3.1)$$

The values of Ψ and Δ were collected for InP, GaAs, InAs and GaP over a wavelength range of 800–1800 nm (0.69–1.55 eV) at temperatures between 25°C (298.15 K) and 200°C (473.15 K) with 10 nm wavelength and 25°C temperature step sizes, respectively [11]. We note that the increased noise on the measured data is consistent with the instrument moving from using a silicon to InGaAs detector for the longer wavelength measurements. This also affects the quality of the fit in the lower and upper wavelength ranges. WVASE® [29] software for the J.A. Woollam spectroscopic ellipsometer data acquisition and analysis was used to develop a physical structure model in which the adjustable fitted parameters were iteratively varied to achieve minimum difference, i.e. the best fit between the calculated model and the measured Ψ and Δ ellipsometric data [29]. For this study, the physical model for the binary compounds samples contains two layers of (i) the substrate and (ii) a thin oxide layer of less than 5 nm thickness. The best fit between model-generated and measured data of InP at room temperature is presented in figure 4a, and its pseudo-refractive index is derived in figure 4b.

For a bulk sample, the pseudo-complex refractive index $[\tilde{n}]$ can be directly calculated from the experimental data [28,29] using

$$[\tilde{n}]^2 = [(n) + i(k)]^2 = \sin(\phi)^2 \cdot \left[1 + \tan(\phi)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1 - \rho}{1 + \rho} \right)^2 \right], \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 4. (a) Generated (solid red) and experimental data (dashed line: Ψ (green), Δ (blue)) fitting for InP at room temperature. (b) Temperature-dependent refractive index of InP derived from the experimental data as a function of wavelength from 800 to 1800 nm over the temperature range from 25 to 200°C.

where n is refractive index, k is extinction coefficient, ϕ is angle of incidence and ρ is the ellipsometric parameters defined by (Ψ, Δ) , as shown in equation (3.1). The SE experimental results undertaken from 25 to 200°C on constituent InGaAsP binaries (figure 5), and their dispersive refractive indices from 800 to 1800 nm were collected. The experimental results demonstrated that at a finite wavelength, the refractive index of the four binaries increased with temperature and was well fitted with the Sellmeier equation model prediction [11]. From this data, the resulting thermo-optic coefficients $(dn/dT) \times 10^{-4}$ (per °C) of InP, GaAs, InAs and GaP binaries at a wavelength of 1550 nm are found to be 1.92 ± 0.06 , 2.40 ± 0.06 , 1.9 ± 0.2 and 1.23 ± 0.02 , respectively (see a more complete discussion in [11]). These temperature-dependent refractive index measurements can then be used in modelling of the active photonic thermometer, as described in §§4 and 5.

4. Indium phosphide-based semiconductors: alloy properties

Having established the temperature-dependent properties of the constituent binaries, the next step is to consider the properties of alloys based on these binary compounds. While the refractive index of a semiconductor tends towards its infrared value for photon energies sufficiently below the band gap, many technologically important applications of near-infrared photonic devices necessitate operating near the band gap (for instance, around 1550 nm on InP). As illustrated in figure 4b, the refractive index of a semiconductor begins to diverge from its long-wavelength Sellmeier-like behaviour closer to the band gap and, as such, it is necessary to account for this when modelling photonic systems.

The spectral behaviour of the refractive index in proximity to the band gap of a given semiconductor alloy can be estimated using so-called single effective oscillator models. One such model has been proposed by Afromowitz [31], which uses material-dependent fitting parameters in addition to the material band gap. These parameters are well-established for binary and ternary semiconductors [4], while the parameters of the quaternary InGaAsP alloy can be calculated via direct weighting of the binary end point semiconductors and higher-order bowing terms using biquadratic interpolation [32].

Figure 5 shows the calculated composition dependence of the room temperature direct band gap (in wavelength units) over the full composition space of $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}_{1-y}\text{P}_y$, alongside the corresponding refractive index at 1550 nm calculated using the model proposed by Afromowitz. The composition dependence of the refractive index is inversely proportional to that of the band gap, with a resonance observed for alloys with band gaps at 1550 nm, consistent with the peak-like behaviour around the band gap observed experimentally. However, we note that for materials approaching InAs, where the band gap drops significantly below 0.8 eV (1550 nm), this model becomes invalid and results in a noticeable overestimate of the refractive index.

Figure 5. Composition dependence of the (a) unstrained material band gap in wavelength units and (b) refractive index at 1550 nm, calculated using a simplified single effective oscillator model [31].

5. Active thermometer design: topology and heterostructures

The basic concept of an active photonic thermometer is to guide and manipulate light–matter interactions using material from group III–V semiconductors that are common active materials for making semiconductor lasers and LEDs. We chose to use these semiconductors owing to both their broad spectral range coverage and the fact that many possess either direct band gaps (such as InP, GaAs and InAs), or can be engineered to have direct band gaps for a given operating wavelength by modifying their composition through alloying [4] as shown in figures 2 and 5. As previously discussed, the band gap and optical constants vary with temperature [3–5], and hence, by forming optical resonators in these semiconductors, it is possible to probe the variation of refractive index owing to temperature changes [1,33–38]. In this work, an RR geometry acts as the optical cavity with path length L and resonance λ_m , where m is the order of the integer multiplication of the resonator wavelength (i.e. resonant mode); we define [35]

$$\lambda_m = \frac{n_{\text{eff}}(T, \lambda) \cdot L(T)}{m}, \quad (5.1)$$

where n_{eff} is effective refractive index of the ring and λ is the operating wavelength. As the temperature changes, the effective refractive index and optical path length also change as a function of temperature, i.e. $n_{\text{eff}}(T, \lambda)$ and $L(T)$, because of the thermo-optic coefficient properties and thermal expansion of the semiconductor ring. Owing to this temperature dependence of the resonance spectrum, it can be used for temperature sensing applications. The development of this photonic thermometry approach towards higher temperature sensitivity depends on the sharpness and intensity of the resonance, which are governed by the choice of the compound semiconductor system (engineering of the band gap energy) and the geometry of the resonant structure. The shift of the resonance ($\Delta\lambda_m$) is due to the change of n_{eff} with respect to the thermal expansion and thermo-optic coefficient of the ring ($\frac{\partial n_{\text{eff}}}{\partial T}$) when the temperature is changed. The temperature-dependent wavelength shift is expressed by [35]

$$\Delta\lambda_m = \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\partial n_{\text{eff}}}{\partial T} \right) + n_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial L}{\partial T} \frac{1}{L}}{n_g} \right] (\Delta T \cdot \lambda_m), \quad (5.2)$$

where n_g is the group refractive index of the ring waveguide, and

$$n_g = n_{\text{eff}} - \lambda_m \cdot \frac{\partial n_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \lambda_m}. \quad (5.3)$$

The separation between each harmonic resonance mode is known as the free spectral range (FSR) [36]:

Figure 6. Simulation of RR behaviour with varying temperature in the range of 75–125°C, (left) wavelength-dependence of transmission going into resonance at 100°C (right) field intensity profile at measurement wavelength.

Figure 7. Heterostructure model of InGaAsP/InP MQW laser as a light emitter of the active thermometer, showing: (a) schematic band alignment diagram with the optical mode profile; (b) schematic illustration of a broad area laser emitter; (c) calculated optical mode coupling in the integrated laser emitter and RR for photonic thermometry applications.

$$\text{FSR} = \frac{\lambda^2}{n_g \cdot L}. \quad (5.4)$$

It follows that a smaller ring gives rise to a larger FSR, which is advantageous in terms of tracking a single mode shift with temperature. However, smaller rings lead to a higher bend loss and are more sensitive to manufacturing tolerance; hence, resonator design must account for this trade-off.

For an initial trial, an RR with a radius of 3.2 μm , a waveguide width of 0.4 μm and a gap of 0.1 μm was modelled for fabrication tests using InP wafers to investigate and develop the fabrication process steps for the full III–V heterostructure. Simulations of the resonant structures were carried out using the Ansys Lumerical 2023 R1 MODE package, where the

Figure 8. Layout design (a) and detailed scanning electron micrographs (b, c, d) of the fabricated InP ring resonator after etching to obtain a $3.2\ \mu\text{m}$ radius, $0.4\ \mu\text{m}$ waveguide width, $0.1\ \mu\text{m}$ gap, and $1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ high ring resonator, with near-vertical side walls and a smooth surface observed.

Figure 9. (a) A waveguide characterization set-up with a lensed fibre and an objective lens for corresponding input and output emission into and from the waveguide under test, mounted on the four-axis stage for translational and rotational adjustment for the best optical coupling between the components. (b) A close-up image of the waveguide aligned with the lensed fibre.

finite-difference eigenmode (FDE) solver [39] was first used to calculate the spatial and spectral profiles of modes by solving the matrix eigenvalue problem across the finite mesh grids of the structure using sparse matrix techniques [39]. Following this, the variational finite-difference time domain method (varFDTD) was used to simulate the propagation of light in the structure. The change of temperature in this theoretical study was accounted for using the temperature-dependent refractive indices derived from the SE data measured from 25 to 200°C . Figure 6 shows the characteristic transmission dip as detected at the end of the waveguide owing to light resonantly coupling into the micro-ring. This demonstrates the resonance spectral shift ($\Delta\lambda_m$) and mode intensity variation of the RR as the temperature changes from 75 to 125°C , achieving the resonance ($\lambda_m = 1552\ \text{nm}$) at 100°C . It can be clearly seen that at resonance, most of the electric field is localized in the micro-ring.

The FDE and varFDTD MODE solvers are also used for calculating the optical mode profile and estimating the effective index and group index of the fundamental mode, as well as the overlap between the optical mode and the InGaAsP/InP multiple quantum well (MQW) laser active regions (i.e. the optical confinement factor) with optical transitions at $1550\ \text{nm}$. The

InGaAsP/InP system has been widely used in the optical fibre telecommunications range, where quantum well heterostructures are well-established, as shown in figure 7 where (a) shows the energy band alignment (top) and refractive index profile and electric field profile (bottom) along the epitaxial growth direction. Figure 7b shows how this is achieved in practice epitaxially, whereby a thin, lower bandgap quaternary InGaAsP layer (of a thickness less than the de Broglie wavelength of electrons, known as a quantum well) is grown in between higher band gap InGaAsP barrier layers, providing quantum confinement for the charge carriers. This forms an active region where light can be emitted (or absorbed) at the target wavelengths of interest. This active structure is then sandwiched between a separate optical confinement heterostructure (SCH) and the wider bandgap semiconductor waveguiding layers with a thickness of around 100 nm as cladding. This provides strong light confinement forming the vertical optical waveguide, as evident in figure 7c. Such a structure provides the basis for the active element in the active photonic thermometer.

6. Initial fabrication trial and outlook towards photonic integrated circuits

For initial proof-of-principle experiments, electron beam lithography (EBL) was employed to fabricate the RR test samples. A series of fabrication trials was conducted, involving variations in resist thickness, exposure dose (measured in $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) and etching recipes to develop an optimized process [40–43]. Parameters such as resist spin-coating speed and time, along with inductively coupled plasma (ICP) etch conditions, were investigated for the InP-based RRs and waveguide system. The critical dimension and etch profile, particularly the gap between the waveguide and resonator after etching, directly influence device performance. Hydrogen silsesquioxane, a high-resolution negative-tone e-beam resist [40], was used as the etch mask. Patterning was carried out using a Raith PG5200 EBL system operated at 100 kV. The layout was carefully designed such that all feature dimensions were integer multiples of the beam step size, helping to minimize artefacts owing to shot noise and grid effects, especially at waveguide edges. Pattern transfer into InP was performed at an elevated temperature (approx. 200°C) using an Oxford Instruments Plasmapro 300 Cobra ICP system with a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ gas mixture. This single-step dry etch process produced RRs and waveguides with near-vertical sidewalls, low sidewall roughness and an etch depth of $1.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. Scanning electron microscopy analysis, including both planar and cross-sectional views (figure 8), confirmed that the optimized EBL process is suitable for fabricating the modelled RRs. In the next steps, prior to on-chip integration of the light source, the resonator and waveguide systems will be characterized using external light injection. An example of this is shown in figure 9, in which a sample of test waveguides is aligned to a lensed fibre for light injection using a four-axis objective stage, a high precision fibre rotator and an achromatic objective lens. This optical set-up for light injection would be replaced in the future process by embedding the III–V active emitters as proposed here. This work provides a promising foundation for the development of active photonic thermometer devices based on InP.

7. Conclusions

In summary, we present a new method of photonic thermometry using active semiconductor materials. We show that the use of compound semiconductors opens up a wide range of possible temperature ranges and temperature sensitivities for photonic thermometry, which may be further engineered through alloying. We also show that the use of direct band gap semiconductors offers a significant advantage over indirect band gap semiconductors owing to

their higher optical transition strengths, which means that light emitters (and strong absorbers) can be embedded directly on the photonic thermometry platform. An exemplar approach using the direct band gap InP material system is discussed, covering initial optical investigations to determine the temperature dependence of the refractive index, where it is shown that the temperature coefficient may be varied through alloying. Finally, the first prototype RR fabrication trials are outlined, confirming that resonant structures can readily be formed in these materials using standard processing techniques highlighting their compatibility with InP-based PICs. This shows promise for the development of these materials for active photonic thermometry and their wider use in large-scale photonic and electronic systems.

Data accessibility. The data contained in this paper are available on Zenodo [44].

Declaration of AI use. We have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article.

Authors' contributions. S.S.: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, validation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; A.Y.: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; D.D.: formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, writing—original draft; C.M.: data curation, investigation, writing—original draft; I.M.: data curation, investigation, writing—original draft; G.M.: conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, validation, writing—original draft.

All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

Conflict of interests. We declare we have no competing interests.

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